

IMPREGNATION MECHANICS FOR THE MELT PULTRUSION OF THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the measurement and modelling of the forces involved when a tow of glass fibre is passed over a cylindrical pin in the presence of nylon 66 resin, as in the melt pultrusion process for the manufacture of thermoplastic matrix composites. A model, based on lubrication theory, is proposed for the impregnation process and is shown to be consistent with the experimental results. The model identifies four distinct flow regions: the entry zone, the impregnation zone, the contact zone and the exit zone.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the manufacture of thermoplastic matrix composites has become possible {1} which has led to some changes in the engineering approach to processing and fabrication. Impregnation is much more difficult with thermoplastic resins because of their higher viscosity (10-100 Pa.s). A number of methods are used to achieve impregnation with thermoplastics, one of the most attractive being direct melt impregnation, or pultrusion, shown in Fig. 1. To optimise operations such as this there is a need for an improved understanding of the mechanics of the process.

The aim of impregnation is to achieve good fibre wetting with a controlled resin volume fraction at the fastest possible throughput, without undue tension build-up in the fibres. With pin impregnation, as discussed by Bijsterbosch et al {2} for instance, it is generally necessary to have several pins to achieve good resin dispersion. There is a progressive build-up of fibre tension from pin to pin, and the fixed geometry wipe-off die produces a further increase. The result is that the line speed is currently limited by the tension build-up in the various stages of the process.

Thermoplastic impregnation can be used to make a variety of useful precursors for processing by injection moulding {3}, pultrusion {4,5} or filament winding.

2. THE PROCESS

When a fibre tow is drawn over a pin in the presence of resin, different regimes of behaviour may be present, as shown schematically in Fig. 2. In describing problems of this type it is often convenient to plot film thickness against circumferential distance (wrap length): Figure 3 shows the way in which the film thickness and tow tension vary with wrap length. Four different

regimes arguably exist:

Region 1: The Entry Zone. Here the fibre tow approaches the pin, at an angle determined by the geometry of the process. As the gap decreases pressure is generated in the resin film separating pin and tow, in a manner analogous to the entrainment of oil in a journal bearing.

Region 2: The Impregnation Zone. The pressure generated in the resin film causes resin to be pumped into the fibre tow.

Region 3: The Contact Zone. This begins when sufficient resin has been pumped through the fibre tow to allow contact between the fibres and the pin. The combination of friction and viscous drag in the residual resin results in a high rate of build-up of tension in the fibre tow in this region.

Region 4: The Exit Zone, where the tow leaves the pin, again at an angle determined by the geometry of the process.

Two reasonable objectives in optimisation of the process would be to maximise the volume of resin pumped through the tow in the impregnation zone and to minimise the tension build-up.

3. THE MODEL

Lubrication theory and Reynolds equation have been used widely to describe and model problems of this type {6,7}. Assuming planar flow (i.e. neglecting sideways flow parallel to the axis of the pin) and adding an extra term to represent the impregnation flow into the fibres, Reynolds equation becomes {7}:

$$\frac{1}{12\eta} \frac{d}{dx} \left(h^3 \frac{dp}{dx} \right) = \frac{V}{2} \frac{dh}{dx} + \frac{\Phi p}{\eta} \quad (1)$$

Φ is the Darcy permeability for transverse flow of resin through the fibres. The description and modelling of such flows with polymers in composite materials are currently being addressed by others {8,9}. For simplicity, Φ will be taken as constant, although it is recognised that it will in fact have a high initial value for a dry tow, decreasing to a lower steady value as resin penetrates through the fibres.

A rigorous treatment, to be reported in a future paper, involves solving Reynolds equation in conjunction with the equilibrium equation for the flexible tow. Analytical and numerical solutions for the case of zero permeability, that of the 'foil bearing', have been discussed in the literature {7,10}. The foil bearing problem has also been investigated experimentally {11} in relation to the passage of recording tape over cylindrical heads. In this problem the film thickness is effectively constant over a large part of the bearing surface, and is given by

$$h_o = 0.643 R \left(\frac{6\eta V}{T_o} \right)^{2/3} \quad (2)$$

In putting together the simple process model described here it was possible to make some simplifying assumptions for each region, enabling some straightforward analytical expressions to be developed. These will be outlined, region by region. A more comprehensive explanation is given in {12}.

3.1. Region 1

In the approach region the pressure build-up is only beginning to take place, so resin flow into the tow will be ignored, allowing the last term in equation (1) to be neglected. Reynolds equation can

then be integrated to give

$$\frac{h^3}{12\eta} \frac{dp}{dx} = \frac{Vh}{2} - Q \quad (3)$$

At some point the pressure will reach a plateau where $dp/dx = 0$. At this point the pressure-induced flow will be zero and the velocity profile across the gap will be linear, so that $Q = Vh_0/2$. This point will be taken to define the exit of Region 1, so in this region

$$\frac{h^3}{12\eta} \frac{dp}{dx} = \frac{V}{2}(h - h_0) \quad (4)$$

The incoming fibre bundle will be assumed to follow a linear path. Near to the point where it approaches closely to the pin (i.e. where $R \ll h$) the gap profile can be approximated to a parabola, so that

$$h = h_0 \left(1 + \frac{x^2}{2h_0 R} \right) \quad (5)$$

Solution of equation (4) is then made possible by the substitution,

$$\tan \gamma = \frac{x}{\sqrt{2Rh_0}} \quad \text{so that} \quad h = h_0 \sec^2 \gamma$$

After making the necessary substitutions, equation (4) can be re-arranged to give

$$dp = 6\eta V h_0^{-2} \sqrt{2Rh_0} (\cos^2 \gamma - \cos^4 \gamma) d\gamma$$

Integrating, and observing that at $x = -\infty$ ($\gamma = -\pi/2$), $p = 0$, this results in

$$p = 6\eta V h_0^{-2} \sqrt{2Rh_0} \left[\frac{\gamma}{8} - \frac{\sin 4\gamma}{32} + \frac{\pi}{16} \right]$$

The pressure at $x = 0$ is therefore

$$p_0 = \frac{3\pi}{8} \eta V h_0^{-2} \sqrt{2h_0 R}$$

For equilibrium, and assuming that $R \gg h$, it can be seen that $p = T/R$ and, neglecting the change in tow tension in Region 1, $p_0 = T_0/R$, so substituting for p_0 and re-arranging gives

$$h_0 = \left(\frac{\pi^2}{128} \right)^{1/3} R \left(\frac{6\eta V}{T_0} \right)^{2/3} \quad (7)$$

Which can be seen to be very similar in form to equation (2). The tow tension build-up in Region 1 is then found to be

$$T_1 - T_0 = \frac{5\pi\eta V}{4} \sqrt{\frac{2R}{h_0}} \quad (8)$$

3.2. Region 2

As the pressure in the impregnation region does not change greatly, the first term in equation (1) will be neglected, so that

$$\frac{V}{2} \frac{dh}{dx} = - \frac{\Phi p}{\eta t} = - \frac{\Phi T}{R\eta t} \quad (9)$$

The length of the impregnation region can therefore be found

$$L_1 = (h_0 - h_1)VR\eta t/2\Phi T_1 \quad (10)$$

Although there is contact between the fibres and the pin at this point, resin occupying the space

between the fibres will continue to produce viscous drag. h_1 is the 'effective' film thickness at this point. Its value can reasonably be expected to lie between the value of the fibre spacing and about half the tow thickness. The tension build-up in Region 2 is given approximately by

$$T_2 - T_1 = \eta VL_1/h_m \quad (11)$$

where $h_m = (h_0 + h_1)/2$. If the total wrap length is less than L_1 , then there is no Region 3 and the tension build-up in Region 2 will be given by equation (12) with $x = L$. In a previous paper, {12} a more complex expression was derived for $T_2 - T_1$. However, equation (11) is now felt to be sufficiently accurate for most purposes.

3.3. Region 3

Here the effective film thickness is constant and, in addition to viscous drag, there is the added possibility of Coulomb friction. The tension build-up can therefore contain two terms, so

$$\frac{dT}{dx} = \frac{\mu T}{R} + \frac{\eta V}{h_1}$$

The solution, for the boundary conditions, $T = T_2$ at $x = L_1$ and $T = T_3$ at $x = L$ is

$$T_3 - T_2 = \left(\exp\left(\frac{\mu L_2}{R}\right) - 1 \right) \left(T_2 + \frac{\eta VR}{h_1 \mu} \right) \quad (12)$$

or simply $T_3 - T_2 = \eta V(L - L_1)/h_1$ when friction is negligible.

Finally, it will be assumed in this simple model that Region 4 does not contribute significantly to tension build-up.

4. COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The use of the model to interpret processing behaviour will be demonstrated, by measurements carried out on the impregnation of glass with nylon 66 melt. These form part of a larger set to be reported in a future publication. Two E-glass tows of 2400 Tex were pulled through a five pin bath at 285°C in the presence of a nylon 66 melt. The pin radius was 10mm and side restraints limited the tow spreading to 20mm. The fourth pin in the bath was instrumented to enable forces to be measured and from these, T_0 and T_1 were calculated. The results were subject to a certain amount of experimental error, estimated at about ±25% for 95% confidence. Moreover, because of the nature of the upstream equipment it was not possible to control T_0 as accurately as would have been desirable. Its average value in the experiments was 30N. By varying the geometry of the resin bath the wrap angle around the fourth pin was varied, enabling the wrap length, L , to be changed. Processing speeds of 5-15 m/min, were used. The results of the experiment are shown in Fig. 4, in the form of plots of tension build-up against wrap length.

5. MODELLING AND DISCUSSION

Equations (8), (11) and (12) describe the tension build-up in the various zones of the process. The model as described so far assumes Newtonian viscosity, whereas the Nylon melt deviates a little from this type of behaviour, obeying

$$\eta = A\dot{\gamma}^{n-1}$$

where, $A = 62.1$ (for shear rates in /s and viscosity values in Pa.s) and $n = 0.81$. In evaluating

the behaviour in Regions 1, 2 and 3 the effective shear rates for calculating viscosity were taken to be V/h_0 , V/h_m and V/h_1 respectively.

In modelling the observed tension build-up there are three parameters that can be varied: the permeability/tow thickness ratio, Φ/t ; the effective film thickness in Region 3, h_1 ; and the friction coefficient, μ . The first two of these can, in principle, be calculated, but both require an in-depth consideration of polymer flow in fibre beds so the calculation will not be performed here. All three parameters were varied and their effect on the predicted values of tension build-up examined. It was found, surprisingly, that the preferred value of friction coefficient was very low for the present results, so this parameter was set to zero.

Good degrees of fit were achieved with a range of combinations of h_1 and Φ/t . A physically reasonable value of 50 microns was chosen for h_1 and Φ/t varied to optimise the fit.

The computed results (for $h_1 = 50$ microns, $\Phi/t = 1.5 \times 10^{-7}$ m and $\mu = 0$) are compared with the experimental data in Fig. 4. It can be seen that, within the range of experimental scatter, there is good agreement between the model and the results over the range of speeds and wrap length studied. For each speed there is an initial region of low tension build-up, corresponding to the impregnation region, followed by a zone of linear tension build-up, associated presumably with the contact region. For the particular system examined the frictional contribution to tension build-up in this region appears to be negligible within the current range of experimental error, although this factor requires further study.

Each of the curves approaches a constant tension value at zero wrap length, the value agreeing quite well with the prediction of equation (8). The predicted values of initial film thickness, h_0 , were 143 and 282 microns respectively for the two velocities. The length of the impregnation zone also increases with increasing speed, as can be seen from Figure 4.

The distance of melt penetration into the tow for one passage over the pin can be estimated as $(h_0 - h_1)/2$. The values of this parameter were 46 and 116 microns respectively for the different velocities. The estimated tow thickness varied from about 150 microns prior to impregnation up to about 300 microns after impregnation, so it can be seen that several pin stages would be required for complete impregnation.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The model has been shown to be capable of describing the experimental tension build-up data for glass impregnated nylon 66 well, so it does therefore appear to be a suitable tool for optimising the process. Finally, for the particular system studied, Coulomb friction in the contact region was not significant.

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Nomenclature

R	pin radius	w	tow width
t	tow thickness	L	overall wrap length

L_1	length of impregnation region	x	wrap length coordinate
h, h_0, h_1	film thickness, values at the end of Region 1 and throughout Region 3	Q p	flow rate/width pressure
T, T_0, T_1, T_2, T_3	tow tension/width, values at various locations	Φ	permeability
η	resin viscosity	τ	shear stress at resin/tow interface
V	velocity		
μ	friction coefficient	γ	shear rate

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Figure 1 Schematic of the pin impregnation process for continuous fibre tows with liquid resin.

Figure 2 Different regions of behaviour in pin impregnation: 1 entry; 2 impregnation 3 contact and 4 exit.

Figure 3 Schematic of (a) film thickness variation and (b) tension build-up versus wrap length coordinate in pin impregnation.

Figure 4 Relationship between tow tension build-up, $w(T_3 - T_0)$, and wrap length for impregnation of two 2500 Tex E-glass tows in nylon 66 resin at 285°C. $R = 10$ mm; $w = 20$ mm. Initial tension = 30 N. Velocity = (a) 5 m/min and (b) 15 m/min. Continuous line is the model prediction for $h_1 = 50$ microns, $\Phi/t = 1.5 \times 10^{-7}$ m and $\mu = 0$. Arrow indicates transition from impregnation region to contact region. Error bars: 95% confidence interval.